

YEAR 2 CONFERENCE PAPERS

Year 2 (5/2018 to 10/2018) Conference Papers from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI)

Conference Papers:

03. Aragón, L.E., Gheibi, A., Masoumi, H., Hedayat, A., (2018) "Geophysical Imaging of Frictional Contacts and Processes in Shaly Sandstone Rock Joints." 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.
04. Cruz, H., Jason NG, Ojeda, F., and Mazari, M. (2018) "Effect of Fiber-Reinforcement on Mechanical Properties of Self-Consolidating Concrete for Transportation Infrastructure Applications." ASCE International Conference on Transportation and Development.
05. Krajnovich, A., Zhou, W., Gutierrez, M. (2018) "A Bayesian Approach to Adaptive and Predictive 3-D Geologic Modeling for Tunneling Projects." 61st AEG Annual Meeting/13th IAEG Congress, San Francisco, California.
06. Gheibi, A., Slouka, S., Hedayat, A. (2018) "Ultrasonic Investigation of Friction Processes in Granular Gouge Materials" 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.
07. Gutierrez, M. (2018) "Effects of Stress, Anisotropy and Brittle-to-Ductile Transition on Fracturing and Fluid Flow in Shales" Proc. European Rock Mechanics Symposium (EUROCK 2018), Russia, Saint-Petersburg.
08. Hedayat, A., Weems, J., Roshan, H. (2018) "Stress and Deformation Analysis of Circular Tunnels With Consideration of Blast-Induced Damage and Gravity." 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.
09. Lu, H., Kim, E., Gutierrez, M. (2018) "A Markovian Rock Mass Quality Q-Based Prediction Model for Tunneling." 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.
10. Ma, S., Gutierrez, M. (2018) "Coupled damage and plasticity model for shear behavior of shale" 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.
11. Martinez, E., Hernandez, J., Rodriguez-Nikl, T., and Mazari, M. (2018) "Resilience of Underground Transportation Infrastructure in Coastal Regions: A Case Study." International Conference on Transportation and Development.
12. Mifkovic, M., Swidinsky, A., and Mooney, M. (2018) "Imaging ahead of tunnel boring machines with DC resistivity: A laboratory study." SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts 2018: pp. 2782-2786.
13. Nelson, P. and Düzgün, Sebnem, H. (2018) "Resilience Impacts from Integrated Above- and Below-ground Urban Infrastructure." ITA-AITES World Tunnelling Conference, Dubai, UAE.

14. Nelson, P. (2018) "Assessing Resilience Impacts from Integrated Above- and Below-ground Urban Infrastructure." North American Tunneling conference Washington D.C.
15. Packman, S., Lopez, S., and Mazari, M. (2018) "Evaluating the Feasibility of Using Soil-Moisture Active Passive Satellite Data to Evaluate Resilience of Transportation Infrastructures." International Conference on Transportation and Development.
16. Prassetyo, S., Gutierrez, M. (2018) "Designing tunnel support systems based on ground reaction curve and equilibrium strain approach." ITA-AITES World Tunnelling Conference, Dubai, UAE.
17. Prassetyo, S., Gutierrez, M. (2018) "Integration of analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in analyzing support requirements for tunneling in weak rock." Proc. European Rock Mechanics Symposium (EUROCK 2018), Russia, Saint-Petersburg.
18. Shirale, D., Walton, G., Ostrovsky, A.L., Hossein, M., Hedayat, A. (2018) "A Non-Linear Ultrasonic Method for Damage Characterization in a Shaly Sandstone." 52nd U.S. Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association, Seattle, Washington.